

Sharf on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Sharf contract on Islamic Financial Inclusion with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key “Sharf” within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Sharf contract based on journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 4 mapping research topics surrounding the Sharf contract, namely: (1) Application of the Sharf agreement; (2) Perspective of Islamic law and Sharf contract legislation; (3) Indicators that influence people's interest in using Sharf contract products; and (4) Other problems with the Sharf contract. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Sharf contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Sharf; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research

Introduction

Currently there are various forms of contemporary economic transactions, such as currency trading. In this regard, how does mu'āmalah fiqh answer various problems regarding contemporary forms of economic transactions today, such as currency trading, the discussion of which in classical fiqh books is still too global. The book of fiqh which discusses the chapter on currency transactions, known as al-sharf, often places its discussion as part of the chapter on buying and selling. In general, buying and selling currency (al-Sharf) in Islamic jurisprudence books is identified with the exchange between gold and gold or silver and silver. Therefore, in the book of jurisprudence, whatever provisions (conditions and pillars) in transactions also apply to currency transactions (al-Sharf), only the categories are more specific. This limitation is understandable, because perhaps in the past, when the book of fiqh was being written by fuqaha, the issue of buying and selling currency was not as prominent a problem as other muamalat issues. In this regard, how does muamalah fiqh answer various problems regarding contemporary forms of economic transactions, such as currency trading, the discussion of which in classical fiqh books is still too global. In the al-Munjid fi al-Lughah dictionary it is stated that al-sharf means selling money for other money. Buying and selling transactions in foreign currency (foreign currency) can be carried out either with currencies of the same type, for example rupiah with rupiah or with those with

different currencies, for example rupiah with dollars or vice versa. Al-sharf is loosely defined as currency issued and used as legal tender in other countries.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding the Sharf contract on Islamic Financial Inclusion using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Sharf contract, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding the Sharf contract, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Sharf contract is a term in Islamic law that refers to an agreement to buy and sell foreign currency. In this context, sharf contract is a buying and selling transaction involving different currencies. This contract is often used in foreign exchange (forex) transactions or foreign currency trading. In sharf contract, two parties agree to exchange a certain amount of one currency for an equivalent amount of another currency at an agreed exchange rate. However, in Islam, there are certain rules that must be obeyed in foreign currency transactions. Some scholars consider forex transactions to be haram (illegitimate) because they involve elements of speculation and usury (interest). However, this opinion is not absolute and depends on the interpretation of each scholar and madzhab. It is important to seek advice from competent ulama or fiqh experts if one plans to engage in foreign currency transactions or sharf contracts in order to understand whether the transaction is in accordance with the principles of Islamic law or not.

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and

compile the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Sharf contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Sharf contracts on Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Sharf " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Sharf contract based on journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Research Topic Mapping using Library Research around Application of Sharf

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found the application of the Sharf agreement in money changers. The following are several steps for implementing the Sharf contract in the money changer:

- (1) **Buying and Selling Foreign Currency:** Money changers will buy and sell foreign currency with their customers. For example, a customer wants to exchange currency A for currency B. The money changer will offer the customer an exchange rate for currency A to currency B.
- (2) **Cash Payment:** The Sharf contract requires payment to be made in cash and directly at the time of the sale and purchase agreement. In the context of a money changer, the customer must pay currency A which he wants to exchange for currency B in cash.
- (3) **Delivery of Currency:** After the customer pays in cash, the money changer will hand over currency B according to the previously agreed exchange rate.
- (4) **No Delay:** One of the principles in the Sharf contract is that there is no delay in the process of handing over the currency. The money changer must immediately hand over the currency purchased by the customer without any delay.
- (5) **Transparency and Agreement:** Before making a transaction, the money changer must provide clear information regarding the applicable currency exchange rate and the fees charged. The customer must agree to the agreement before the contract is carried out.

The implementation of the Sharf contract in money changers aims to ensure that foreign currency buying and selling transactions take place in accordance with sharia principles, such as cash payments, transparency and delivery without delay. This ensures that transactions are carried out fairly and in accordance with Islamic sharia rules.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Islamic Legal Perspectives and Legislation Sharf

Based on a review of Library Researchs in previous research journals, researchers found the perspective of Islamic law and Sharf contract legislation, including:

First, sharf in muamalah fiqh. In the context of muamalah fiqh, sharf agreement refers to an agreement or contract that involves buying and selling using different types of currency. The term "Sharf" itself refers to "exchange" or "exchange" in Arabic. In the muamalah fiqh tradition, it is generally recommended that buying and selling transactions be carried out using the same type of currency. However, in situations where the two parties involved in a transaction have different currencies, sharf contract can be used to facilitate the exchange. In sharf contract, both parties agree to exchange one type of currency for another currency at a certain exchange rate. This exchange must be made in cash and immediately without any delays or additions. In this case, currency exchange becomes the main object of the contract, not the goods or services that are usually traded. To ensure that Sharf's contract complies with the principles of muamalah fiqh, there are several conditions that need to be met, including:

- (1) Currency exchange must be done in cash and immediately, that is, both parties must exchange currency directly without any delays or additional time.
- (2) The currency exchange rate must be clear and agreed upon by both parties before the transaction is carried out.
- (3) The Sharf contract must be carried out voluntarily and agreed between the two parties involved.
- (4) Transactions must be carried out fairly and there should be no elements of fraud or manipulation in currency exchange.

However, it is important to note that the Sharf contract is controversial in some muamalah fiqh perspectives, especially in cases of currency speculation or ribawi (interest-bearing) transactions. Some scholars consider it incompatible with Islamic principles which prohibit usury and speculation. Therefore, in practice, Sharf contracts may have additional limitations and conditions that differ in each context and view of jurisprudence.

Second, sharf according to classical scholars. According to classical scholars, the Sharf contract has several important elements that must be fulfilled so that the transaction is valid and in accordance with Islamic principles, including: (1) Ijab and Qabul: Ijab is an offer from one of the parties indicating the intention to sell goods, while qabul is the acceptance of the offer by the other party. Consent and qabul must be clear, firm and agreed upon by both parties. For example, the seller clearly states his intention to sell the item, and the buyer clearly accepts the offer. (2) Objects Traded: The objects traded in sharf contract must be clear, specific and measurable. Goods traded must be halal and not violate Islamic principles. For example, the goods traded must not be haram, such as alcohol, pork, or stolen goods. (3) Ownership: The seller must have legal ownership of the goods to be sold. There must be no defects in ownership or claims by other parties to the goods. The seller must have the legal right to sell the goods to the buyer. (4) Payment: The purchase price must be clearly and firmly agreed upon by both parties. Prices should be specific, not vague or ambiguous. There must be no element of fraud or gharar (excessive uncertainty) in price determination. (5) Additional Terms and Conditions: There may be additional terms and conditions that can be determined by both parties,

as long as these terms do not conflict with Islamic principles. These conditions must be clear, not create excessive uncertainty, and not violate Islamic law. Classical scholars such as Imam Syafi'i, Imam Maliki, Imam Hanafi, and Imam Hambali have discussed and developed these principles based on their understanding of the Koran, Hadith, and the opinions of the companions of the Prophet Muhammad SAW. These principles form the legal basis of Sharf contracts in the classical ulama tradition.

Research Topic Mapping using Library Research around Indicators that Influence Community Interest in Using Akad Sharf Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found indicators that influence people's interest in using the Sharf contract, including:

First, product innovation. _ Product innovation can be an indicator that influences people's interest in using Sharf (foreign currency exchange) contracts in the following ways: (1) Ease and Speed of Transactions: Product innovations that enable foreign currency exchange quickly and easily will attract public interest. For example, developing a mobile application or online platform that allows users to easily access and carry out foreign currency transactions directly from their devices. This eliminates the need to go to a bank or physical financial institution to exchange foreign currency, thereby simplifying and speeding up the transaction process. (2) Additional Features and Functions: Product innovations that offer additional features or useful functions can increase people's interest in using Sharf contracts. For example, integration with popular electronic payment systems or digital wallets, so users can easily store and transfer foreign currency. Features such as notifications of the latest currency exchange rates, graphs of currency movements, or market analysis can also increase people's interest in using the product. (3) Security and Privacy: Security and privacy are important factors in foreign currency exchange. Product innovations that provide a high level of security, such as data encryption and protection against leakage of personal information, will make people feel comfortable using Sharf contracts. If a new product can offer a better security system than the current one, people's interest in using the product will likely increase. (4) Competitive Fees and Commissions: Low or competitive fees and commissions are an important factor in attracting people's interest in using Sharf contracts. If product innovation can reduce transaction costs or offer lower commissions compared to other alternatives, then people will be more interested in taking advantage of it. For example, reduced interbank transfer fees, lower currency conversion fees, or offering competitive price spreads. (5) Education and Information: Product innovations that provide comprehensive education and information about foreign currency exchange can help increase public interest in using the Sharf contract. For example, providing tutorials or interactive guides on how to use the product effectively, providing access to the latest currency market news and analysis, or providing useful investment recommendations.

Second, location. Location is an important factor that influences people's interest in using the Sharf contract (foreign currency exchange) in the following ways: (1) Accessibility: The geographical location of an area can influence people's interest in using the Sharf contract. If a region has easy access to global financial centers or foreign exchange markets, then interest in exchanging foreign currencies through Sharf contracts will be higher. For example, areas close to financial centers such as New York, London, or Tokyo will generally have greater interest in using Sharf contracts due to the availability of complete

financial facilities. (2) Tourism and Trade: Locations that are tourism destinations or have high international trade activity tend to have greater interest in using Sharf contracts. This is due to the need for foreign currency exchange for payments in foreign countries, sales of products and services to tourists, or investment in international trade. For example, locations such as Paris, Dubai, or Singapore have a high interest in using Sharf contracts due to their significant tourism and trade activities. (3) Policies and Regulations: Location can also influence people's interest in using Sharf contracts through government policies and regulations regarding foreign currency exchange. Some countries may have policies that limit or regulate foreign currency exchange, while others may encourage and provide incentives for their citizens to use Sharf contracts. These factors can influence people's interest and comfort in using the Sharf contract. (4) Financial Infrastructure: The existence of financial infrastructure that supports foreign currency exchange, such as banks, money changers, or other financial institutions, is also an important factor that influences people's interest in using Sharf contracts. If a region has a good network of these institutions, with easy access to foreign currency exchange services, then interest in using the Sharf contract will be higher.

Third, promotion. Promotion can influence public interest in using the Sharf contract (foreign currency exchange) in the following ways: (1) Awareness: Effective promotion can increase public awareness about the benefits and advantages of using the Sharf contract. An informative marketing campaign can educate the public about how the Sharf contract works, the potential savings that can be earned, and the protection it offers against currency fluctuations. (2) Trust: Promotion that is trusted by the public can help build trust in the Sharf contract. Using testimonials or recommendations from satisfied users can help strengthen people's confidence in the reliability and profitability of foreign currency exchange using the Sharf contract. (3) Special Offers: Promotions may include special offers, such as discounts or lower transaction fees, to encourage people to try Sharf contracts. The financial benefits offered in the promotion can be an attraction for people to use the Sharf contract rather than other foreign currency exchange methods. (4) Education: Promotion can provide educational information to the public about the differences between the Sharf contract and other foreign currency exchange methods. In this promotion, it is important to clearly explain the benefits, safety and legality of the Sharf contract, as well as answer common questions that the public may have. (5) Benefits and Convenience: Promotions that emphasize the benefits and ease of use of the Sharf contract can attract public interest. For example, promotions can highlight the easy and fast process of using Sharf contracts, as well as benefits such as lower transaction costs, higher liquidity, and flexibility in meeting foreign exchange needs.

Research Topic Mapping using Library Research regarding Other Problems in the Sharf Agreement

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found problems surrounding the ethics of foreign exchange exchange from Sharf's contract perspective. In the context of the Sharf contract (sale and purchase agreement in Islamic law), there are several principles and ethics that need to be considered in foreign exchange exchange. The following are several things that need to be considered:

- (1) Buying and selling must be carried out by mutual agreement: In sharf contract, foreign exchange exchange must be carried out based on

- mutual agreement between both parties. There must be no element of fraud or coercion in the exchange process.
- (2) Clarification and Transparency: All relevant information regarding the currency to be exchanged must be conveyed clearly and transparently to both parties. There must be no manipulation of information or fraud regarding the condition of the currency to be exchanged.
 - (3) No Riba: Riba (interest) is prohibited in Islamic law. Therefore, in a foreign exchange exchange, no interest element must be added or received by either party.
 - (4) No Excessive Speculation: Forex exchange in Islamic law should not involve excessive speculation or gambling. The purpose of forex exchange should be to meet real transaction needs, not to seek purely speculative profits.
 - (5) Balanced Exchange: In a foreign exchange exchange, the exchange rate used must be balanced and fair for both parties. There must be no exploitation or imbalance that harms either party.
 - (6) Timely Delivery: Each party in a foreign exchange exchange must fulfill its obligation to deliver currency according to the agreed time. There shall be no unfair delays or non-compliance with the agreements that have been made.
 - (7) Permitted for Halal Purposes: Forex exchange in Islamic law is permitted as long as it is used for halal purposes. For example, foreign exchange for travel, trade or legitimate business transactions.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 4 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding the Sharf agreement on Islamic Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Application of the Sharf agreement; (2) Perspective of Islamic law and Sharf contract legislation; (3) Indicators that influence people's interest in using Sharf contract products; and (4) Other problems with the Sharf contract.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA

- PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of*

- Research in Management*), 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>

- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>

- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni*, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>